

Oil painting: The Paint Quality and The Material

The paint quality

[Portrait painter](#) Jared Ailstock shares that the paint is composed of finely ground mineral or organic pigments, mixed with oil which hardens as it dries. There are different color qualities which correspond to the fineness of the pigments and their concentration. Jared Ailstock shares these qualities:

* The study quality is intended for painters who practice a lot. The colors are packaged in large tubes and the prices are more affordable.

* Extra fine grade is the oil with the highest pigment content. There is usually only one pigment ground with no chemical additives. The range of colors available is immense, it is the oil par excellence.

* Fine quality is quite simply between the previous two.

Jared Ailstock claims that in order to choose the quality that meets your needs, you should study the fine qualities that are strong enough for thick work while the extra-fine quality is recommended for fine applications where you will need a strong coloring power.

You can very well start with the extra fine quality and restrict yourself to a range of primary colors that will allow you to create all the others.

[Jared Ailstock](#) shares a choice of colors to obtain a complete color chart:

- a lemon yellow
- two reds: vermilion and dark madder
- an ultramarine blue + a Prussian blue
- two extra browns: ocher and burnt sienna
- a titanium white
- an ivory black

Black can be obtained by mixing: dark blue + dark red + yellow). Subsequently, depending on your needs, you can purchase more vivid colors.

The palette

Jared Ailstock shares there are classic wooden or plastic palettes.

You can also use:

- * a white melamine board
- * a sample of tiles
- * disposable pallets to avoid the drudgery of cleaning

Jared Ailstock indicates that the advantage of oil painting is that you can leave your palette aside for several hours without the colors drying out.

If you are new to oil painting, practice good habits. On your palette, the order of colors will respect the chromatic circle: warm colors together and cool colors like blue or magenta on the other hand. For more information, visit Jared Ailstock's [profile on Speakerhub](#).